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XR Stories Industrial Strategy Response

A University of York Policy Briefing
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University of York & XR Stories

The University of York is a world-class research institution, with strong links to the creative industries and has for more than 20 years conducted applied research at the convergence of engineering, science, arts, humanities, and social science. This work is University-wide with particular strengths in the School of Arts and Creative Technologies, the School of Physics, Engineering and Technology, and the Departments of Computer Science and Psychology.

Based at the University of York, [XR Stories](#) was founded as an Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded Creative Industries Cluster Partnership (CICP) and between 2018-2024 it provided £3.5m of funding to SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) working in virtual production (VP) and extended reality (XR). It continues to provide researchers, companies and creatives with access to expertise, infrastructure and facilities to unlock the potential of XR (extended reality) technologies and next generation convergent media technologies. XR Stories also leads the 2022-2027 Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) [XR Network+](#) VP in the Digital Economy project, which brings together five universities to undertake research into the future of VP and to fund co-created projects between academia and industry.

The work of XR Stories builds upon a series of major research projects relating to creative technologies at the University of York. Since 2014, the EPSRC [Intelligent Games and Game Intelligence Centre](#) for Doctoral Training has been developing the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers, designers, developers, and entrepreneurs for the games industry. From 2015-2022 the EPSRC/AHRC/ Innovate UK (IUK) funded [Digital Creativity Labs](#) worked with creative industries partners to maximise impact from research in digital games, interactive media and AI. From 2020-2024 the Research England [Screen Industries Growth Network](#) (SIGN) introduced a portfolio of research, skills development, business support and diversity and inclusion interventions to complement XR Stories. Most recently, 2023 saw the launch of the University of York led [CoSTAR Live Lab](#), one of five labs forming a connected infrastructure, funded by AHRC to support future R&D (research and development) in the screen and live performance industries.

Executive Summary

In November 2024 XR Stories submitted a response to the UK Government's 'Invest 2035: the UK's Modern Industrial Strategy' Green Paper. The evidence presented in this response focused only on the Creative Industries as identified in the industrial Strategy as one of eight growth-driving sectors that will be prioritised. This policy briefing provides a summary of the key points outlined in the response. These points are summarised as follows:

Support convergent creative industries subsectors with proven R&D and growth potential

- The creative industries are a major growth driver for the UK economy, exporting products and services to a global market.
- The screen and VP sectors are expanding rapidly, supported by world leading infrastructure, VFX and creative tech supply chains and government investment.
- R&D and innovation in CreaTech and XR technologies backed by sustained government investment are central to sustained sector growth.

Policy and regulatory support for creative applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Intellectual Property (IP) protection

- AI and Machine Learning (ML) are transforming creative workflows offering new opportunities for convergent innovation.
- However, this also poses a significant risk to creatives' livelihoods through automation and exploitation of IP.
- Global regulation and IP protection frameworks are urgently needed to guarantee fair use, attribution and remuneration for creators of work used in the training of AI/ML.

Further strengthening of regional innovation and place-based clusters

- The UK's screen and virtual production industries remain highly concentrated in London and the South-East, persisting regional disparities in creative sector development.
- CICP and CoSTAR initiatives are driving place-based regional innovation and R&D in the creative industries bringing industry together with universities.
- Increased and sustained regional investment aligned with national and pan regional policy initiatives are key to expanding growth of the creative industries across the whole of the UK.

Address barriers to SME R&D by investing in skills, training, and inclusive talent pipelines

- Skills and talent shortages are major barriers to growth across the creative industries, particularly in emerging areas of VP and CreaTech that demand high turnover of skill sets.
- Inequalities in the workforce and poor working conditions persist at the detriment to growth, with more investment needed targeted towards inclusive growth.
- Opportunities for SMEs and freelancers to access creative R&D infrastructure are severely lacking, more needs to be done to help small businesses scale up.

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Recommendations

1. Support convergent creative industries subsectors with proven R&D and growth potential

The UK has a world-leading track record in the creative industries, through the content we make and the IP we create across the sector and export worldwide: with the GVA of the creative industries estimated at £123.03bn in 2024, equivalent to 5.37% of total UK GVA. In 2021 the creative industries exported £54.73bn of creative goods and services (8.35% of total UK exports)¹. This is supported by a skilled workforce, studio and production infrastructure, a large freelance and SME sector and supply chain, and the UK's world-leading university sector providing both a future talent pool and R&D capacity and capability.

In 2021 the BFI produced a report analysing the economic impact of these subsectors between 2017-2019² noting:

“In 2019, the screen sector value chain generated 156,030 full-time equivalent (FTE) jobs (ie from direct, indirect and induced impacts) in comparison to 132,300 in 2017”

“UK-made productions generated £13.48 billion in overall GVA, a 23.7% increase”

“Production spend and related job creation led to the generation of significant tax revenues for HM Government, estimated for all tax relief screen sectors in overall terms to be £3.60 billion in 2019”

¹ <https://www.wearecreative.uk/cultural-and-creative-industries-stats-q1-2025-26/>

² <https://www.bfi.org.uk/industry-data-insights/reports/uk-screen-sector-economy>

The UK screen industries are investing heavily in new studio infrastructure, with demand for production space currently outstripping supply³ with recent significant developments and investment going into Belfast ([Studio Ulster](#)) and Sunderland ([Crown Works](#)) amongst others.

The convergence of media technologies and the spillover from this impact as games industry technologies influence other subsectors of the creative industries (and beyond)⁴, has led to VP becoming an alternative workflow to traditional film and tv production pipelines. This is a fast moving and global phenomenon in which the UK is arguably a global leader.

“The virtual production industry worldwide is projected to reach a projected revenue of 6.8 billion dollars by 2030. With an expected annual growth rate of 18.2% from 2024 to 2030⁵.”

The US has a projected annual VP growth rate of 15.5%⁶, whereas the UK has an expected annual growth rate of 18.4%⁷. The UK is therefore well placed to capitalize on the opportunities provided by the global growth of VP and related technologies, and with the right investment and policy interventions from government, the UK could consolidate its world leading position for VP R&D and innovation with the effect of attracting more international productions to the UK bolstering the UKs creative industries through further inward investment. The Department for International Trade has highlighted the UK’s unique position of possessing established infrastructure, a skilled workforce, a world class visual effects (VFX) supply chain and a demonstrated ability for agile innovation around creative technologies⁸.

XR technologies are already disrupting workflows in film, television, theatre, live events, social media, heritage/ tourism, digital gaming and home working, and becoming embedded in training, healthcare and sales amongst other markets. The 2022 Immersive Economy Report⁹ noted more than 2,100 XR technology companies in the UK, an 83% growth over the previous five years, with a significant proportion being micro-SMEs, and 80% having 1-9 employees. This is reflected in our own data where more than 92% of companies supported through our XR Stories/ XR Network+ R&D funding are SMEs, micro-SMEs, sole traders or freelancers.

In the first round of the AHRC Creative Industries Cluster Programme that funded the XR Stories project, nine university-led Creative Clusters were awarded. Six clusters were predominantly focused on screen

industries innovation (film, TV, games and related media, encompassing the Department for Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) Creative Industries subsectors of ‘Film and TV’ and ‘IT, Software and Games’), two focused on fashion (‘Design and Fashion’) and one cluster broadly considered data in the creative industries. These successful creative cluster projects demonstrate where a sector has been able to evidence a critical mass of companies working together within a subsector and a growth trajectory founded on university-led collaborative R&D. It is notable the skew towards screen industries and Creative Technology (CreaTech) that underpins this first round of AHRC investment. CreaTech is a term that is used to describe innovation at the intersection of creativity, arts, culture and technology, with a recent DCMS report¹⁰ highlighting the growing importance of CreaTech to the UK economy and society more widely. This trend is supported further through the subsequent AHRC CoSTAR programme that secured more than £76m of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) investment for R&D infrastructure to support the future of screen and live performance industries in their intersection with CreaTech.

The DCMS creative industries subsector definitions are well defined although broad in the range of businesses that they encompass, noting also that businesses are not always well matched to Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes, especially given that agile, technology focused companies may work across a number of subsectors. Given that developing the capacity for SMEs to partake in R&D is one factor to drive growth across the creative industries, the identification of more relevant subsectors potentially advantages those that rely more on the development and use of CreaTech to generate new IP as this has become a key driver to R&D across the sector .

In recent years there has been significant investment via UKRI to support R&D in the creative sector (especially via AHRC and IUK) through open competition. It follows that a wealth of data should exist to help understand the profile of those companies working in specific subsectors of the creative industries that have identified their potential for growth through R&D, and those who have been successful in applying for these opportunities.

³ <https://www.lsh.co.uk/explore/research-and-views/research/2021/july/film-studios-research-report-2021>

⁴ <https://ukie.org.uk/resources/the-economic-impacts-of-video-game-technology-spillover>

⁵ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/virtual-production-market#:~:text=The%20global%20virtual%20production%20market,18.2%25%20from%202024%20to%202030>

⁶ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/horizon/outlook/virtual-production-market/united-states>

⁷ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/horizon/outlook/virtual-production-market/uk>

⁸ https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/60a2e06021577f542777ca5d/624c09e7718ea4285e66bb00_DIT%20UK%20Virtual%20Production%20Review%20FINAL%20March%202022.pdf

⁹ <https://iuk.immersivetechnetwork.org/resources/the-2022-uk-immersive-economy-report/>

¹⁰ <https://royalanniversarytrust.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/CreaTech-Report.pdf>

2. Policy and regulatory support for creative applications of AI and IP protection

Underpinning all of these new convergent technologies are the advances in AI and ML as they become integral to creative workflows, and, through generative AI, content creation. While the rise of AI offers enormous potential for innovation at the intersection of creativity and technology, it also represents a serious threat to the livelihoods of a large proportion of the creative workforce, both in terms of infringing on creator's intellectual property during the training of models and job losses due to automation of labour.

Creative industries companies and individuals are much more aware of their IP being used in various generative AI models and how this may lead to loss of authorship,

control and revenue or exploitation by other companies and organisations. Legislation and ethical use need to be considered and put in place to protect IP for individuals and the content they create, and this will need to work across different global territories. Legacy materials and assets (both personal and material) also need to be considered and how they might be repurposed for future digital experiences. Regulation around IP, creative content and the impact of AI is key in order to properly compensate the originators of new work.

3. Further strengthening of regional innovation and place-based clusters

In 2023 47% of UK businesses involved in film/TV production were based in London, accounting for 83% of total turnover in the UK¹¹, followed by the South-East (18% of businesses, 5% of turnover). Contrast this with Yorkshire and Humber with 3% of businesses and 0.7% of UK turnover. 60% of UK VP companies and 54% of studios are also based in London and the South-East¹².

The AHRC CICP was predicated on the value of academic/industry partnerships that capitalise on regional areas of strength and excellence in the creative industries, and led to the delivery of a programme of targeted place-based innovation. The CICP was designed in response to the recognised contribution that the geography of the creative industries makes to the UK economy, with a view to driving continued long-term industry growth. The programme was designed to create links between research undertaken in universities and the creative industries and, then, at the city/region level, to deliver economic benefits associated with R&D investment and cluster development including an expansion of capacity among creative businesses to exploit technical and data-driven innovation. This is the first time that a national innovation programme targeted regional rather than national economic development with 107 spin-outs, start-ups and scale-ups created, with the creation or safeguarding of 3,413 FTE employees, and supported businesses leveraging £57m in investment, co-investment and follow on funding from public and private sources.

The AHRC CICP and CoSTAR programmes, together with the IUK Audiences of the Future and Creative Catalyst programmes have all helped to support SMEs with R&D, with CICP in particular leveraging the capability and convening powers of regional universities to support this

activity¹³. Current support for CoSTAR via UKRI/AHRC is time limited to 2029. Although it is expected that private sector commercial income will support its continuation in part, it is imperative that core UKRI funding continues such that the majority of its activities remain within the remit of the public sector and hence responsive to industry needs, and particularly the needs of emerging businesses and SMEs.

Some aspects of CreaTech production pipelines and workflows lend themselves to supporting the growth of companies in other ways - the networked nature of production infrastructure has opened up more opportunities for remote working roles, and for the crew that are required to work on site, the requirements to travel for location work are significantly reduced. The CoSTAR investment also reflects this trend with networked facilities coming online in Dundee, Belfast and Yorkshire.

With the Creative Industries already highlighted as a key area as part of The Industrial Strategy, this initiative will work to align and prioritise existing policies and plans in this sector across the regions. The Creative and Cultural Sectors have been highlighted as key growth opportunities for the regions of the North of England, with the Northern Creative Corridor initiative¹⁴ giving rise, in part, to the One Creative North programme¹⁵ with a vision to grow the North's Creative Industries through a collaboration across Northern Mayors and leaders. The newly formed York and North Yorkshire Mayoral Combined Authority has highlighted Creative and Digital Sectors as an emerging area of strength to be further supported, and alignment with the Industrial Strategy will only accelerate this plan.

¹¹ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/business/activitysizeandlocation/adhocs/2258theukfilmindustry2022and2023>

¹² <https://craic.lboro.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Virtual-Production-Ecosystem-Mapping-March-2023-Final.pdf>

¹³ <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/AHRC-01072024-FRONTIER-BOP-CICP-CRDP-final-evaluation-report-STC2-20240524.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://www.thersa.org/reports/creative-corridors-connecting-clusters-to-unleash-potential-report/>

¹⁵ https://pec.ac.uk/news_entries/one-creative-north-plans-finalised-at-summit-ahead-of-convention-of-the-north/

4. Address barriers to SME R&D by investing in skills, training, and inclusive talent pipelines

Skills

The lack of a suitable skills base and readily available talent pipeline is another barrier to investment. The evolution of (particularly) screen industries via VP, CreaTech and AI is a combination of arts and humanities, design and engineering and computer science skills. Future roles will require a combination of creative and technical skills, and careers advice in schools, work experience and curriculum development should adapt to understand this potential. Existing experts in technical, production and supporting functions will also need to either retrain or update their skills and support to do so should be widely available. XR Stories have just announced one such programme of creative technology skills development supported by the new York and North Yorkshire Combined Authority, and focused on creatives, including freelancers, working across this region.

The micro/freelance nature of the creative industries makes skills development for roles difficult, including those focused on CreaTech, due to the need to self-fund courses and a lack of opportunities to formally learn on the job. Training interventions and diversity schemes have provided opportunities to acquire skills needed by industry, often via embedded internships or placements. However, a lack of long-term funding impacts their success, often seeing schemes ending just as they are implementing

second iterations of their work. To address this problem, predictable long-term funding is required to sustain training (and R&D) schemes that target diverse cohorts at all stages of their career development, benefitting workers, production companies and the industry as a whole. Furthermore, schemes should be available in the region where workers live – to reduce time and travel costs – and productions take place – to meet local needs. Funding could be sought from those that profit from a skilled workforce e.g. production companies, broadcasters and streaming platforms.

Equality, diversity and inclusion

The advent and development of creative technologies has been identified as a unique opportunity to address the systemic imbalances in equality, diversity and inclusion that exist in the screen industries and creative industries more widely. Support for policy interventions to support the inclusive development of creative industries is a key strategy identified by many research groups looking at methods of improving equality, diversity and inclusion in the UK creative industries. Recommendations for promoting gender equality in CreaTech contexts include collecting baseline gender employment data, setting challenging

targets to address imbalances, adoption of gender-inclusive recruitment packages, and running outreach sessions to show that a career in these creative technology areas is viable for women¹⁶. Legislation to improve creative industries workers and freelancers conditions of work is also recommended. Long working hours, precarity, and cultural issues lead to certain groups leaving the industry or limiting their capacity to work¹⁷.

¹⁶ https://screen-network.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/57311-Briefing-paper-008_inclusion-and-gender-diversity_6pp_WEB.pdf

¹⁷ <https://filmtvcharity.org.uk/research-impact/reports/absent-friends-report/>

Investment

Although creative businesses can access seed and angel funding, investment drops off at scale up stages. Investment events involving CreaTech companies tend to raise between 22% to 34% less than other comparable examples¹⁸. CreaTech companies have seen a consistent growth of investment, having raised £981.8m in venture capital investment during 2020, an increase of 96% since 2017, but a question might be raised about how long this growth is able to continue without access to later stage investment¹⁹.

Government funding comes from multiple departments (Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (UKRI), Department for EDUCATION (DfE), DCMS) resulting in limited focus at the expense of creating programmes that can address, for example, both skills and R&D support. Even within UKRI there is lack of coordination between AHRC

(CICP, Immersive Arts, CoSTAR), IUK (Creative Catalyst), EPSRC (e.g. the Digital Economy Programme - which no longer exists as a priority area).

New business models need to be identified and developed to exploit the commercial possibilities around the distribution and sale of CreaTech driven new media and immersive experiences. Any SME transitioning into or entering this market needs to adapt to these new business models. The SMEs that make up the majority of the UK Creative Industries Sector lack capacity to conduct R&D without risk to their core business. Providing tax credits and other financial incentives for CreaTech focused aspects of the Creative Sector will be important in maintaining the UK's position as a world leader through our innovative SMEs and their global market.

¹⁸ <https://pec.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/PEC-An-analysis-of-Creattech-RD-business-activity-in-the-UK-v3-1.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://www.thecreativeindustries.co.uk/download-hub/the-creattech-2021-report-release>

Infrastructure

In 2022 a report from the Department for International Trade identified the UK as the worldwide epicentre for feature film VP stages, possessing the largest number of Tier 1 stages and the second largest number of all VP stages, behind the USA. However, a large number of these facilities are owned by a small handful of multinational conglomerates, with access being expensive due to high day rates driven by demand from advertising and high-end film / TV productions. Access to creative technology facilities for R&D is therefore particularly challenging

for freelancers and SMEs, while most facilities that are accessible for R&D are via universities or e.g. Digital Catapult, and therefore either restricted in availability or subject to short term funding pressures. While it is anticipated that the AHRC's £76m CoSTAR programme should go some way towards addressing this issue, further sustained investment is required to provide SMEs and freelancers with sufficient access to creative technology R&D facilities.

Contact

For further information, or to request a copy of the full response document, please contact jay.harrison@york.ac.uk

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